

**TRENDS in Pediatric Palliative Care Research (TPPCR) 2026; Issue #06: Commentary on
Bishop, C. et al.**

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Abstract:

This TPPCR commentary discusses the 2026 paper by Bishop, C. et al., Finding comfort in complexity: The role of palliative care in children with leukodystrophy, in the Journal of Molecular Genetics and Metabolism.

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While there are numerous research studies highlighting how earlier, integrated and specialized pediatric palliative care (PPC) can improve care for children (Marcus et al., 2019), this month's articles exemplify how this service is rolling out around the world and show how important expanding into new clinical settings and more diagnostic areas can be for implementation. This month's articles also highlight how shifting the narrative can impact the service uptake.

Over time palliative care consult has been known to help with challenging symptoms, creating trust among clinical teams and assisting with advance care planning. Not all clinicians, however, refer to palliative care when a child could benefit from the service. Our feature article this month in Trends by Bishop and colleagues explores referral rates specifically for leukodystrophy (Bishop et al., 2026). About 30% of children with leukodystrophy die at an early age. Early onset and aggressive forms of leukodystrophy are a major factor for dying at a young age. However, research from a chart review study of 206 children with leukodystrophy in an 8-year period found that only about a quarter of those (26%) had a referral to palliative care recorded in their medical records. The average referral time was 2.4 years from diagnosis to consult. This interval spans about half of their short lives (average age at death was 5.2 years) although presumably dying children were seen sooner. Of the 53 children with consults, 41 died and of those, 63% had been seen by palliative care. This represents a fraction of children who could have benefitted from symptom management, clinical communication and advance care planning, regardless of whether they died. Furthermore, those who did have a consult waited years if they got one at all. Nearly 14% of the children who died of leukodystrophy in this sample did not have a palliative care consult.

Another chart review study looked at implementation of palliative care for children with heart failure over a five-year period in Saudi Arabia (Sadler et al., 2026). In that study, of 47 children treated for heart failure, over a third (43%) died during the study period. In Saudi Arabia and parts of the Middle East, newly developed palliative care programs are slowly being implemented in those countries (Alotaibi et al., 2023). This developmental stage offers a unique window to study both the implementation, and assess effectiveness, of integration into usual clinical care.

One last relevant article described shifting the narrative to include earlier and more impactful PPC (Stewart et al., 2026). This excellent assessment of language and framing science examines how thinking about palliative care is important and how challenges abound in narrative and current communication models. These challenges often prevent referral to palliative care, impacting clinician behaviour and parental understanding of the services offered.

Early adopters of palliative care services such as psychosocial oncology teams were instrumental in supporting palliative care in children (Kaye et al., 2016). These oncology teams, with their integration of research and advanced study trials, were able to identify those diagnostic groups who were at high likelihood of dying at a young age. As children live longer with medical complexity, research into life expectancy and the use of palliative care in children with genetic and neurological disease is advancing alongside. This research is emerging and hopeful for our field.

In my bedside role as a pediatric hospice nurse, children with rare diseases are sometimes known to us for years. Children come for respite when they are “well” and we enjoy time in the hospice with their families, with siblings playing alongside them in the garden playground. This way the

clinical team builds a relationship with the family and can ideally provide better care for them when crisis hits. Introducing palliative care early for children with leukodystrophy would be beneficial for these children, who are also candidates for respite care given their fragility. PPC can also help alleviate the heavy burden of caregivers who care for them.

New diagnostic groups, new clinical settings and shifting the narrative can all result in earlier palliative care referrals, which may ameliorate caregiver, patient and sibling psychosocial factors while also helping with pain and symptom management. There is a long way to go, and we continue to see disparities in diagnostic, clinical location and language and framing conventions.

References

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